

MEDICAL SCIENCES

FAMOUS DOCTORS OF THE ANCIENT EAST AND AZERBAIJAN

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Abstract

People living in Azerbaijan several thousand years ago already had medical knowledge, and this stage was developing in an upward trend. This rise, which was founded in the VIII-IX centuries, lasted until the end of the XIV century. Ancient East and Azerbaijani doctors Abu Mansur Muwaffaq, Abu Sahl Masihi Jurjani, /Ibn Sina's teacher/, Ibn Sina, Ibrahim Ibn-Ali-Najjar-Khagani Shirvani, Abu Nasr al-Farabi, Muhammad Zakariya-ar-Razi, Abu Reyhan Biruni, Kafiyaddin Omar Osman oglu, Isa al-Raqqi Tiflis, Muhammad Yusif Shirvani, Murtuza Gulu khan Shamlu fluent in Arabic and Persian, visited, studied and worked in various cities of the Caliphate, such as Baghdad, Damascus and Cairo.

Keywords: doctor, medicinal plants, pharmacology, drugs, historical source, manuscript.

It is no exaggeration to say that in the tenth and fourteenth centuries, the Islamic world was the pinnacle of human civilization. The largest universities, observatories, hospitals, pharmacies and libraries were located in the Muslim East, where the most powerful scientists worked.

During this period, madrasas operated under large mosques in Azerbaijani cities. These madrassas taught Arabic and Persian languages, Arabic grammar, logic (religious dogma), jurisprudence (Islamic law), mathematics, calligraphy (calligraphy), history and eternity. Greek philosophy, astrology, logic, public speaking, geometry, medicine, alchemy, and other subjects were taught in large madrassas, similar to modern universities. The children of the landowners and the clergy read here.

Azerbaijani doctors, fluent in Arabic and Persian, visited, studied and worked in various cities of the Caliphate, such as Baghdad, Damascus and Cairo. Books by foreign authors also found their way to Azerbaijan.

During this period, the pharmacological encyclopedia of Abu Osman Muwaffaq al-Haravi was distributed in Azerbaijan. Although Abu Osman lived and worked in the 10th century in the Iranian province of Herat, his books were popular throughout the Muslim East, including Azerbaijan. In order to gather information about medicinal plants, Abu Uthman traveled all over the world and got acquainted with the medical traditions of many peoples, including Azerbaijanis.

One of the first researchers in the field of pharmacology and pharmacology, Abu Mansur Muwaffaq, a prominent physician, pharmacologist and pharmacologist of the 10th century, probably came from Northern Azerbaijan and wrote the first book of pharmacology in 980.

The "Scientific Work on the Fundamentals of Pharmacology" written by Mivaffag or Abu Mansur in the late tenth century is noteworthy. This work is important as a source of information on chemical knowledge, the development of methods for the preparation of preparations containing plant extracts. The

scientific work shows simple methods for obtaining essential oil and distilled water. Also, chemical compounds are prepared - cinnabar and suleiman for the treatment of skin diseases; copper sulfate for the treatment of eye diseases; natural soda in plant powder as an astringent and blood-stopping agent, alkalization of carbonate during consumption, astringency, natural borax used as a medicine under the name of "nushdar", nashatir, and finally oxide, and especially zinc sulfate used by the Arabs in the treatment of eye diseases. Later, Abu Mansur described the characteristics of gypsum and arsenic, antimony, iron, clay, copper, lead, gold, silver, oil, resin, camphor, starch, kamed, soap-based oils, etc., in simple form and in hardened form. showed. The book also tells about the ancient means of fras - ointments from mercury and alkane. Abu Mansur also mentions the use of some organic acids in medicine, such as corn sugar and tannins.

Abu Mansur's book explains the effects of 446 herbal and 44 animal medicines.

Before writing the book, the author traveled to Iran and India, studied the drugs used for treatment, and noted that he encountered many difficulties here.

The author shows that the effect of drugs depends on the individual characteristics of the body, ie the body's heat, cold, dryness and humidity. He noted that the effect of drugs on the body goes in three stages: during the circulation of the drug after taking it and when it is eliminated from the body. Therefore, when a doctor prescribes a drug to a patient, he must determine these characteristics, as well as the taste of the patient, the drug and the diet, and monitor the effect of the drug. He gave strange explanations about the effects and use of drugs. For example, he put forward ideas about toxic drugs, poisons, opium (a form of medicine), their preparation and use.

He expressed unimaginable opinions about the quality of medicines, food, food and medicine at that time. The same drug can have different effects on the same patients. Therefore, treatment should be carried out individually.

Ali Asadi systematized Abu Mansur's book on pharmacology in the 11th century and translated it from Arabic into Persian.

Abu Mansur suggested very interesting ways of injecting drugs into the body: eating, drinking, rubbing, wet, dry, blowing, tampons, wicks, etc. Here he paid special attention to the treatment of asthma, skin and prostate diseases.

Abu Mansur considered it necessary for a person to be his own doctor. He said that a person can determine the cause of changes in the body by observing the individual characteristics of his body.

Abu Mansur's book on pharmacology was published in 1892 in Derpt in German. The translator and author of this book was the Azerbaijani doctor Mirza Abdulkhalig Akhundov. According to this publication, he received the title of Doctor of Medicine. A brief copy of the book was written in Persian in 447 AH, 1055 AD and is now housed in the Vienna Library.

Akhundov Abdulkhalig Haji Abdulla oglu was born in 1866 in Baku. After graduating from high school in Baku, he entered the medical faculty of the University of Derpt / Tartu / and graduated with honors from the Department of Ophthalmology.

Later, at his father's request, he went to Germany to study medicine at the University of Erlanger and received a diploma in psychiatry. Over the years, he has mastered ancient Greek, Latin, German, French, Russian, French, and Arabic.

Returning to Baku at the end of the 19th century, Abdulkhalig Akhundov is actively involved in socio-political and cultural spheres. Creates a library, publishing house. Participates in the enthusiastic activities of Baku intellectuals.

What is the healing effect of music? The famous Central Asian Turkish scholar Abu Nasr al-Farabi (873-950), who has encyclopedic knowledge, states in his book "The Great Book of Music": "Music promotes the improvement of mood, moral education, restraint and spiritual development. It is also good for the physical health of the person, because when the body is sick, the spirit is also weakened. Music, which has a positive effect on the human senses, improves mood and restores health to the body.

At that time, doctors were trained in mosques, madrassas, secondary schools, and universities in Azerbaijan. While training specialists in these schools, special attention was paid to their formation as individuals. They taught education, science and helm, that is, deontology, the rules of ethical conduct. Therefore, clergymen, doctors, philosophers, historians, architects, mathematicians, writers and other specialists were honorable in fulfilling their artistic and civic duties in their fields, being knowledgeable, scientific, healthy and humble. Their names were also mentioned with honor. It is no coincidence that the doctor, the judge and the philosopher were popularly called "doctors". The reason for this is the release of people from former scientists and doctors,

The IX-XII centuries are a period when medical science was especially formed and developed. Famous medical figure, philosopher Muhammad Zakariya-ar-Razi / Arabic /, Abu Mansur Muwaffaq / Azerbaijani /,

Abu Reyhan Biruni, Abu Sahl Masihi Jurjani, / Ibn Sina's teacher /, Abu Ali ibn Sina / Tajik 980-1037 /, Omar Osman oglu / Azerbaijani / and so on.

The IX-XII centuries AD were the period of formation of medical science in the east. One of the prominent scholars of this period was Abu al-Hasan Ali Rab-bani al-Taabari, who lived in the early ninth century. The author used Greek and Oriental literature to write the book "Firdovsi-ul-Hikmat" in Arabic (236 h 850 m.).

One of these personalities is Ali ibn Abbas Majusi Ahwazi / 994 /. This scientist is the author of the book "Kamil ul-sanat tibb".

Another of these eminent scholars was Abu Sahl Masihi Jurjani Isa ibn Yahya, the teacher of Ibn Sina (died in 1003).

The genius Abu Ali Ibn Sina (980-1037) also visited Azerbaijan many times and collected medical information from there. He tells about his visit to Saburkhist settlement of Azerbaijan in his work "Qanun fith-tibb" ("Laws of Medicine"). Ibn Sina lived for a long time in the city of Hamadan on the borders of Azerbaijan, where he wrote most of the "Laws of Medicine".

Abulqasim Zahravi's (died in 1013) book "Surgery and Instruments" is a valuable example of art that has survived to this day.

In Europe he was known as Abulcasis. The work contains images of surgical instruments developed 1,000 years ago. It is included in the UNESCO Memory of the World list

Dastur-ul-Alaj, which occupies a special place in the medical literary heritage of the East, is one of the most important books on treatment. H 993, m Written in 1526 by Sultan Ali Khorasani.

The author writes, "I have been practicing medicine in Khorasan, Samarkand and Mavarannahr for more than 40 years. At that time, I was working with Dr. Abu Mansur Guggu. The disease has spread in the country. Abu Mazaffar Mahmud Shah invited me and ordered me to write a book on medicine. "

The author mentions that he has used many books and adds his own experience.

The book discusses the role of the pulse in treatment methods and the crisis that occurs during the course of the disease - the crisis. The introduction of the book deals with hygiene, ie the scientific and practical tasks of medicine.

There are also written about diseases of the body, their symptoms - symptoms and prescriptions for treatment.

In addition, the source of energy of the air and a necessary factor of life, the relationship between spirit and body, the effects of seasons, temperature on health and physical activity, cities, places of residence, housing hygiene, seasonal clothing, food hygiene. It also explains the efficient use of water and water, the prohibition of wine and its use, and the serious consequences of overuse, sleep patterns, and the benefits of exercise. The rules of administration, emetic drugs and their use, bleeding and hemorrhage are indicated.

Mental and psychological states - information about the effects of pleasure, peace of mind, fear, shame, thoughts, anger, hope and despair on the body.

One of the prominent scientists of Azerbaijan was the uncle of our famous poet Ibrahim Ibn-Ali-Najjar-Khagani Shirvani, the great organizer of science and health, doctor Kafiyaddin Omar Osman oglu. The successor of Ibn Sina's school, Kafiyaddin was also a great philosopher, mathematician, astronomer and chemist.

Umar ibn Usman Kafiaddin is by origin the most famous doctor-scientist among the Azerbaijani Turks. In Shamakhi, he created and operated a health house there, from where his fame spread throughout the East.

About Omar Kafiaddin 1080 - in Shirvan, the capital of Shamakhia, it is believed that he was born in this city. He was one of the most outstanding personalities of his time, and his fame as an Azerbaijani scientist spread everywhere. Kafiaddin was a highly educated person. He knew several languages, was well versed in philosophy, theology, astronomy, mathematics, medicine, chemistry and pharmacology, and taught at a madrasah. Khakani wrote about him: "If my uncle does not leave me, no devil can lead me astray. He is a man of culture and science. As water rises in height under the influence of the sun, so I have risen thanks to it. , is the Arastun of his time."

It is said that before establishing his own healing center, Omar Kafiaddin instructed his students to slaughter several sheep and hang them around Shamakhi. A week later, Kafiaddin drove through these places one by one and saw that the corpses were damaged everywhere. The meat hung in a place called Birja Melhem remained as if it had just been butchered. From this Kafiaddin concludes that the air in the ointment is not only very clean, but also has a healing value. Therefore, he decided to establish his medical academy here.

And now this place is called Mazyu. Azerbaijani scientist N.K. Karamov believes that the name of this place comes from the word "ointment" in our language - a valuable medicine. There is another version about the origin of the name of this place. There is a legend that a doctor lived in the vicinity of Shamakhi, who once treated skin diseases with a miraculous ointment, and the place later received the name "Mazh". Kafiaddin invites medical scientists to work here, involved in treatment, drug production and medical education. He was an excellent doctor, surgeon and pharmacist. Like other similar establishments in the Middle East, his hospital had a pharmacy. Doctors, pharmacologists and pharmacists of various specialties also lived here. At the same time, recruits, full-time doctors and pharmacists, including "surgeons".

In the treatment centers of that time, the corridor system of buildings was usually applied. There were reception and procedure rooms at the entrance, wards on either side of the corridor, and finally a morgue at the end of the clinic. The main building was connected to the farm building by an open balcony. The balcony improved air conditioning in the building and was used as a ward when needed. A small pharmacy was located a short distance from the main building. Nearby, houses for doctors and servants were built, as well as a large pharmacy. The pharmacy went to the garden, where

various plants were planted to prepare medicines. According to MA Akhundov, "The Academy used molds for the treatment of various internal and external diseases. Up to 17 types of these fungi were distinguished: bread mold, milk mold, confectionery mold, honey mold, etc."

Omar Osman oglu taught his students moral purity, patriotism, and service to the people, just as he was demanding of himself: "You do good to the people, even if you hurt yourself," "Do not be selfish," and so on.

He adhered to the ideas of the East, such as "Man must be his doctor," "He must study his body well," and he himself repeated it. At the same time, he said, "Medicine has a cure for all ailments, but doctors do not know all of them. Take care of yourself, don't trust the doctor. "

Omar Osman oglu considered the brain to be the center of life activity and showed that the body's balance, memory and cognition depend on its condition.

Omar Osman oglu was also a great pharmacist. His extensive arsenal of medicines included animal, mineral and herbal medicines. He also made extensive use of diet, physiotherapy, and organ therapy.

Omar Osmanoglu's methods of treatment were in line with his views when the disease occurred in the 11th century. He believed that in case of malnutrition and overeating, the culture should be cleaned and vomited. In this case, he preferred sour milk taken during heating. He treated heart disease with honey, syrup, sweet wine and fruit juices. During kidney disease, he ate boiled borax and root with honey and grape juice. Omar Osmanoglu also used organ therapy: he treated his grandfather with hedgehog oil for oral administration, he used crushed animal bone powder for joint pain, and for mild diseases he used animal brain powder, egg yolk and "fodder" grass collected early in the morning. has done.

Kafiaddin's son Vahidaddin Osman is also a great help in his activity. Osman was a good doctor, surgeon and pharmacist with encyclopedic knowledge. He was also known as a perfect philosopher, theologian and poet. He was also a talented musician and musicologist. He was well versed in music theory and played the erkan, the father of the modern argan. Osman Xaqani He also took an active part in his upbringing. It is not ruled out that the poet received his musical education from Osman.

Umar ibn Uthman Kafiaddin 1150 died in and Shamakhi. He was buried with great reverence. Here, in the hot mountains under the constant rays of the sun, among the tall trees, juicy grasses and abundant water springs, patients could be healed without a doctor. Later, this place turns into a flea. The people, who sincerely believed in the sanctity of these places and the scientist buried here, came here to worship and offer sacrifices. The name "Dada Gunesh" is derived from the name "Dada" given to Kafiaddin among the people. At the same time, there is a saying among the people used to warn people against weeds, which also mentions Kafiaddin Dada: "Do not play with this grass like Dada. It is poisonous, let the horse go." Khagani lamented Kafiaddin's death:

Oh! Gone is the philosopher of this world,
The meaning that opened the door of heaven went,
alas!

In addition to medical sources, there is extensive information about mental illness in oral folk medicine, folklore, and in the pages of the literary heritage of poets and ashugs, great thinkers.

Mental deficiency in the Azerbaijani language is defined by many words: crazy, insane, depraved, rabid, hot, key, crazy, stupid, stupid, stupid, stupid, stupid, and so on. The people of Azerbaijan treat such patients with patience and care.

The first work reflecting the state of medicine in Azerbaijan was "Medicine" by Isa al-Raqqi Tiflis. Isa al-Raqqi was a representative of the empirical direction. For him, experience is a "powerful factor" that solves everything, theoretical discussion is abstraction, "experience is creation, abstract judgment is destruction." Jesus al-Raqqi opposed the theories of the existence of the soul. According to him, the organism is a whole living being, and the disruption of one part leads to the disruption of the whole organism. Here you can determine your health and illness.

As a remedy, Isa al-Raqqi recommended a variety of foods, herbs and minerals. For example, in the case of kidney and intestinal diseases, he treated it with very sweet remedies: honey, grapes, fruits, sweet pomegranate. In gastrointestinal diseases, a diet was maintained to cleanse the stomach. He also used sour milk, grape leaves (for skin diseases), cherry jam for sore throats, and opium "when nature is disturbed."

While traveling to many countries, Isa-ur-Raqi became acquainted with their medical problems, and in addition to translating many works, he enriched them with his science and experience.

In his writings, Isa-ur-Raqi showed that experience is the decisive factor.

He recommended the devastating effects of bad habits and the need to avoid them: "If every body could not accept bad habits, it would not be addicted to them, so it cannot give up bad habits (drugs, alcohol, cigarettes, etc.)."

Among the good customs, Jesus-ur-Raqqi meant food, rest, movement, cleanliness, tidiness, restraint and patience in his time. They must be obtained as a result of the study of past experience, the mysteries of nature, their theoretical verification and analysis. Therefore, the heritage of medicine and pharmacology should be studied at the level of these principles and modern understanding. It should also be noted that the origin, development, emblem, and foundation of medicine and medicine are the same, and the common goal is to heal. Nevertheless, as a result of the development of these sciences and arts and the expansion of their fields of activity, medicine and pharmacology began to develop as independent fields of science and art in 754, with the aim of uniting them with action forever.

The development of modern medicine and the production of hundreds of new effective drugs should not prevent us from studying the great heritage of Eastern medicine. Serious complications and drug diseases, especially those caused by chemical drugs, lead us to relearn Oriental medicine. The history of pharmacology

consists of studying and applying its rich experience, as well as the totality of human knowledge and experience in the fight against diseases and their prevention.

This should be done by pharmacists who are committed to their art. It also depends on the art, effort and diligence of pharmacists.

According to religious law, medicine is a field of science and art that works to ensure the physical and mental health of people.

It is well-known that when a person is physically ill, he also suffers spiritually. When you are mentally ill, the normal functioning of the body is disrupted, and the person becomes mentally and physically anxious. Therefore, a doctor can become a doctor only if he can feel the patient's pain, determine the cause of his illness and his taste, prescribe the right treatment, gain the patient's trust, and not disturb the patient-doctor relationship. The doctor's task is to heal the patient and be able to enjoy him spiritually. Therefore, a doctor must know both medical and religious sciences, he must have a deep philosophical outlook, and a doctor must be wise and humble, as well as a wise psychologist. As a true master of his art, he must be able to approach the patient individually. He must be able to understand not only the mood of the patient, but also the mood of those around him. Because a relative, especially those who serve the patient are mentally and physically disturbed. It is no coincidence that the late Fuzuli said the following about those who served the patient:

"Service to the patient who sees, in the end he became ill"

The physician and pharmacist must fear God and memorize the Hippocratic oath, repeat it daily, and observe it. After prescribing treatment to a patient, the doctor should monitor the progress of the disease, because the same disease does not go the same way in all people.

Most of the physicians involved in the treatment, as well as the attars, were engaged in the collection and drying of medicinal plants with their students. Doctors sent copies of prescription drugs to pharmacies and prepared them there.

In the past, there were attar pharmacies in most cities and villages of Azerbaijan. For example, Shamakhi, Shusha, Ganja, Aghdam, Nakhchivan, Lahij, Ordubad, Salyan, Lankaran and others. These pharmacies had a wide range of herbs and spices. For example, in the attar pharmacy of Mirbaba Mir Abdulla oglu, the father of Yusif Vazir Chamanzaminli, more than a hundred of the 142 medicines were herbs.

However, currently 5-6 green pharmacies operating in the country do not have 20-25 such medicinal plants. However, in the pages of medical literature of that time, including Mirza Mehdi Naqtash Ganjavi's / 1791 / book "Garabaddin", hundreds of drug names were included in 74 drug forms. Among them are anushdaru, paste, cuvarish, torture, vodka, zimad, pills, ointment, hakna, ayaraj and others. can be shown. However, currently the number of dosage forms does not exceed 20. The words "May God heal" were written in the recipes as "Huvallahu shafa".

Mansur ibn Muhammad ibn Yusif ibn Ilyas, one of the great Azerbaijani scholars, was born in Tabriz in

the 14th century, later moved to Shiraz and worked there for a long time. and the author of other valuable books. He described thousands of herbs and other natural remedies and various treatments. This scientist became famous in Iran and other Eastern countries.

In the works of Mansur ibn Muhammad ibn Yusuf ibn Ilyas, there is a special chapter in his book "Medicine" ("Medicine", 1436) entitled "Rules for the preparation of medicines." He was a supporter of the rule that in the treatment of the disease it is necessary to treat the body with general strengthening agents, directly affecting the diseased organ. In his comments, the scientist pointed out the occupational diseases of nomads, painters, doctors, weavers and advised them to follow the rules of hygiene for the above professions. He advised painters, leather gloves and wooden spoons to mix, leather carvings for nomads, and always drank butter-milk after lime work. In the technology of preparation of medicines, Mahmud described the uselessness and incompatibility of the preparation of reciprocal neutralizing agents: vinegar-milk, acid-alkali, etc. With the exception of some notes on its harmfulness, it has not introduced any innovations.

Oral folk medicine (Turkish remedies) has a special place in Azerbaijan.

Among the books on medicine, works on medicine have a special place. Of these, the book "Makhzan-ul-Adviyya" (Treasure of Medicines) by Mohammad Hussein Alavi, which is of great scientific and practical importance / 1032 pages, date of writing 1771 / was republished in India in 1888. In writing this work, the author used the works of medieval medicine and the works of Ibn Sina, Ibn Baytar, Sheikh Yusuf Baghdadi, Sheikh Dawud, Abu Rayhan Biruni and others, as well as the ancestors of the physician's descendants.

The second authoritative "Garabadin" is the work of Muzaffariddin Ibn Ahmad Ibn Hussein al-Shafa'i.

The third work "Garabadin" is a book written by Mirza Mehdi Naqtash Ganjavi skillfully and creatively based on the work of Shafai / in 1786 /. These books show 74 forms of medicine and their different types, more than 1000 prescriptions and in what diseases they are used. There is no doubt that the analysis and application of these works at the level of modern understanding will have a great social and economic effect.

In the 13th century, there were geniuses and other doctors of Azerbaijan, such as Ibn Kabir Khoi, Muhammad Ibn Namvar Tabrizi. Recent research shows that 724 species of medicinal plants are described in medieval Azerbaijani manuscripts. Many of them have already been forgotten by modern medical science.

The works of Ramadan ibn Sheikh Ali Lan-Karani (late 13th century) were noteworthy. In one of them, in the work "Far-ruh-name Jamali" (1409), the author spoke about the healing properties of organic and inorganic drugs, showed the therapeutic quality of milk, brain and stomach. Azerbaijan at the service of this author's discovery of therapeutic mud and determination of the healing properties of Azerbaijani clay - gialba.

One of the valuable examples of the Middle Ages is the Tohfah-ul-Mu'min - / contribution to the believers / 1277 h. / 1863m. It was written by Mahammadali Tehrani and published in Dar al-Khilafah in Tehran. The

author shows that Akhund Mola Ali and Seyid Hussein Isfahanni helped him to write the book. He also mentions the authors who wrote before him in Persian and Arabic: Shaykh-ur-Ra'is, Ibn-Ashdas, Abu Hanifa, Yahya Ibn Chozla, Jarjas Ibn Yuhanna, Sayaf, Amin al-Dawla, Ibn Talmin, Ibn Baytar, Sheikh David, shows doctor Ali Gilani.

Gives information about the essence, effect, dosage of spices - in snake and scorpion stings: it means to squeeze, scratch, suck and burn a living area, for example, and sometimes to cut that area. The book provides information on weight units. It is a drug used to treat various diseases of the body.

In the Elkhanid state established in the XIII-XIV centuries, science reached very high peaks. The flourishing of medical science in Azerbaijan dates back to the XIII-XIV centuries. Most likely, it was during this period that reflexology (acupuncture and staining) began to spread in Azerbaijani medicine. Remains of this ancient method of treatment still live under the name "childak".

Azerbaijani scholar Najmaddin Ahmad Nakhchivani wrote comments and borders on Ibn Sina's works on medicine and philosophy. Nakhchivani Najmaddin ibn Ahmad ibn Abubakr ibn Muhammad (born in Nakhchivan, died in 1253 in Aleppo, Syria) - a well-known Azerbaijani philosopher in the Muslim East, studied in Nakhchivan, perfectly studied all areas of science. He lived part of his life in Azerbaijan and worked at the Maragha Observatory. The Arab scholar Ibn al-Ibri (Abu-1 Faraj; 1226-1286) wrote about Nakhchivani in his "A Brief History of the States" ("A Brief History of the States"): was engaged in philosophy. "Nakhchivan had to leave his homeland, probably due to political circumstances. The philosopher, who was the vizier of Amir Jalaleddin Garatay for a while, could not remain indifferent to the socio-political events around him when he witnessed injustice in the upper circles. He left the palace life as a sign of protest and went to Aleppo. Ibn al-Ibri writes:

"He traveled his countries, traveled a lot, and finally came to Rome, where he held senior positions."

The scientific and philosophical creativity of Nakhchivani was highly appreciated by medieval authors. The Arabic author Ibn Bibi likened it to "a rippling sea and a rainy cloud in all sciences and disciplines" and noted that it contained religious and secular sciences. Nakhchivani studied the problems of peripatetic philosophy in depth and attached great importance to logic and natural science. Despite being considered an active promoter of the works of Ibn Sina, a prominent representative of Arabic-speaking peripateticism, he critically examined a number of doctrines. Nakhchivani wrote commentaries on Ibn Sina's books "Law of Medicine" and "Signs and Notes". Unlike the Eastern peripatetics, Nakhchivani, who believed in the existence of the soul after death, "had a strong tendency to the doctrine of sexuality," according to the sources. . He did not examine Ibn Sina's works from the point of view of orthodox Islam, but criticized the peripatetics by accepting a doctrine that did not conform to the principles of the ruling ideology. Manuscripts of his works are in

various archives around the world, including a commentary on the book "Law of Medicine" in the National Library of Paris, a commentary on the book "Signs and Notes" in the Turkish Hagia Sophia, Nur Ottoman and Bridge libraries, "The essence of logic and a summary of philosophy" in Najaf, Iraq. -Mashhad al-Alvin is kept in the manuscript fund.

The famous doctor Abu Abdullah Muhammad Ibn Namwar Tabrizi (1194-1245), who lived and created in the city of Tabriz, is the author of the work "Advarul-hammiyyat" ("The most important medicines").

Another doctor, Yusif Ibn Ismail Khoi, better known as Ibn Kabir, was one of the most prominent pharmacists in Azerbaijan and the Muslim East in general. His Jamei-Baghdadi (Baghdad Collection), written in 1311, was considered one of the most complete works on medicine in the whole East. He was one of the most famous pharmacists of the XIII-XIV centuries. He was born in Khoy, South Azerbaijan, where he studied medicine, and later moved to Baghdad, where he became a court physician for the caliphs. In 1311, Yusuf ibn Ismail wrote a pharmaceutical encyclopedia called "Jamei-Baghdadi" ("Baghdad Collection"), which became famous throughout the East. The book covers several thousand medicinal plants, minerals and animals used in medicine.

Scientists from Nasreddin Tusi's scientific school have also created a number of important medical works. One of these scholars is Abdulmajid Tabib. In about 1275-1280, he wrote the book Kitab al-Mudawat. In addition to psychiatry, neurology, sexopathology, the book examines many other topics of medicine.

During the Safavids, a number of prominent doctors grew up in Azerbaijan. Yusif Garabaghi emigrated from Azerbaijan in the 17th century and lived in Samarkand, where he taught in a madrasah. He wrote commentaries and margins on Ibn Sina's Qanun. The people of Samarkand called him "Great Akhund" as a sign of respect.

Murtuza Gulu khan Shamlu was known as a specialist in sexually transmitted diseases. In addition to being a scientist and doctor, he was the governor of Ardabil (1678) and one of the Safavid emirs.

The activity of Muhammad Momin (died 1697), originally from Mazandaran, was also connected with Azerbaijan. He was a court physician of Shah Suleiman the Magnificent and created an encyclopedia of medicine and pharmacy called "Tohfatul-Mumin" ("Contribution of Believers", 1669) by order of the Shah.

During this period, the works of a number of Central Asian, Persian and Arabic authors became famous in Azerbaijan. The following works were the desktop books of Azerbaijani doctors: Ali Ansari (Haji Zeynalabdin Attar) "Ikhtiyarati-badii" (XIV century), Yusif Ibn Muhammad Haravi "Jamul-fawaid" or "Tibbi-Yusifi" (1511), Mansur Ibn Muhammad "Kifayatul-mujahida" or "Kifayeyi-mansuriyya" (1423), Sultan Ali Khorasani "Dusturul-alaj" (XVI century), Sayyid Mir Muhammad Momin "Tohfatul-mu'minin" (1669), Muzaffar Ibn Muhammad Hussein Shafai "Garabadin" (XVII century), Muhammad Ibn Ali Naghi "Zadul-musafirin" (XVIII century), Muhammad Hussein Khan

Alavi Samarkandi "Makhzanul-adviyya" and "Garabadini-Kabir" (1777) and others.

A number of medical works of Ottoman Turks also found their way to Azerbaijan. Some of them are now kept in the Institute of Manuscripts of ANAS: Dervish Nidai "Manafaun-nas" (XV century), Mohammad Raisul-Atibba "Unumuzajut-tibb" (XVII century), Mustafa Feyzi "Risaleyi-ginagina" (XVIII century) and others. One of the manuscripts of Manafeun-nas was copied by the Azerbaijani secretary Mohammad Attar Salyani in the 19th century. There is also a copy of "Tibbname" from the period of the Ottoman Sultan Murad, copied by Muhammad Yusif Shirvani in 1711/2. The book was written in Ottoman Turkish and deals with the treatment of most diseases known at that time.

At the end of the 17th century, Haji Suleiman ibn Suleiman Arivani's Fevand uo-Hikmat appeared. Here the names of medicines are written in different languages - Azerbaijani, Arabic, Persian, Greek. The author indicates the load limit used in the preparation of medicines:

1 rhythm is equal to 90 mica or 360 grams;

1 men is equal to 180 mica or 720 grams;

1 miskal is equal to 4 grams (in Ibn Sina's Qanun, miskal is equal to 4.25 grams).

In addition to plant, mineral and animal products, Azerbaijani folk medicine has applied water and mud treatments, oil and sun treatments, and massage.

Arivani divided the drugs into categories: the first category included a certain amount of substances that do not cause changes in people with moderate hyperactivity. The second category includes substances whose effects are clearly observed. The substances were "harmful" in the third degree, but did not have a dangerous effect. The latter effects are specific to substances belonging to the fourth degree.

In practice and in comparison, Azerbaijani pharmacists have identified the properties of medicines. According to them, the experiment should be carried out on young and healthy people with moderate enthusiasm. The time of year and day were taken into account. It was recommended to repeat the experiment at different times of the year. It was necessary to prescribe the most appropriate number of drugs for treatment. The study needed to start with small doses and gradually increase them.

Among the experiments, the results of experiments on animals could be considered. At the same time, it should be borne in mind that the same substance from different animals could have different effects. It is also important to keep in mind that herbal remedies or the plant itself could have been a natural product for animals to eat, and that it could have had a powerful effect on humans if they had eaten them.

When determining the properties of any herbal remedy, the place where the plant was collected, the time of collection, and the condition of the plant (fresh, dried) must be taken into account. Herbal and animal medicines had to be stored for some time to prevent loss of properties. In this regard, it was always necessary to indicate the time of harvest of the plant and to know the duration of storage of plant raw materials.

Chapter XIII provides information on units of weight, and Chapter XIV provides information on celestial bodies. Chapter XVII is devoted to the definition of diseases, their definition, degrees, symptoms and treatment.

Pharmacist Mohammad Momun, who lived in the 17th century, has already given herbal extracts for the treatment of skin cancer (carcinoma). Modern research in the United States and Europe has confirmed that these ancient manuscripts are indeed effective. Recently, hypericum perforatum has been widely used in medicine in the United States. Doctors recommend it to treat mild forms of depression. In 2000 alone, \$ 160 million worth of drugs were sold in the country. However, the anti-depressant effect of daziot was noted in medieval Azerbaijani medical manuscripts, in the works of Haji Shuleyman Irvani and Hasan Ibn Reza Shirvani in the XVIII century. These facts prove once again the wisdom and deep knowledge of our ancestors.

Hasan Ibn Reza Shirvani, who lived in Shamakhi in the 18th century, wrote Sirajut-tibb (The Lamp of Medicine). This book deals with hundreds of complex medicines (pills, candles, pastes, ointments, powders, etc.).

Haji Suleyman Gajar Irvani's work "Fawaidul-Hikmat" ("Benefits of Wisdom") is dedicated to pharmacology. It lists thousands of natural remedies and shows how to use them. Yerevan's manuscripts are preserved in Azerbaijan, Iran, Egypt and other countries.

The Garabadin (pharmacopoeia) written by Seyid Muhammad Hussein khan in 1185 AH and 1771 AD consists of 20 chapters.

Chapter 1 of the book states: Nutrition is essential for human survival, and food affects the soul as well as the human body. Writes about the importance of water in the digestion and absorption of food. At the same time it definitely explains the issues of food and poison.

Chapter III of the work deals with taste and its types, four main features of the human body - cold, heat, dryness, humidity and so on.

In the twentieth chapter, his grandfather, doctor Mir Mohammad Hashim, talks about Seyid Alavi khan and Mir Mohammad Hadi Alavi and others. The remaining 15 chapters of the book are devoted to medicine. While writing this book, he came across the manuscript of his grandfather Mir Mohammad Hashim (known as the doctor Mutamad ul-mulk Seyid Alavi khan). This manuscript shows that Mir Mohammad Hashim wanted to write "Garabadin", but the work was incomplete.

Among the hundreds of scientific, literary and medical manuscripts preserved at the Republican Institute of Manuscripts, the work "Tibbname" written by Muhammad Yusif Shirvani in 1124 AH and 1712 AD attracts attention. This manuscript consists of 114 pages and 120 sections.

Muhammad Yusif Shirvani is one of the famous scientists, doctors and calligraphers of Azerbaijan who lived in the late 17th and early 18th centuries. Muhammad Yusif Shirvani was born and raised in Shamakhi, where he studied medicine and studied medicine. He was a doctor under Lutfali bey, the butler of Shirvan beylerbey Huseyn khan. In 1711/2, Muhammad Yusif

Shirvani copied the cover of the unknown work "Tibbname" and wrote an introduction, comments and explanations. Thanks to his service, this book has survived to the present day. "Tibbname" is one of the most important medieval medical works in the Turkish language. This book deals with the treatment of most diseases known at that time.

"Tibbname" was the first medieval medical work published in Azerbaijan in 1990 in the Cyrillic alphabet for a wide readership. The book was later translated into Russian and published in St. Petersburg. Tibbname is the first medieval source on medicine in Azerbaijan, published in Russia.

Muhammad Yusif Shirvani (1704-1813) in his work "Tibbi-noma" summed up the views existing in Azerbaijan up to that time. Compiled by the author in the Azerbaijani language "Dictionary of Oriental Medicine", "Norms of treatment in the works of well-known scientists, various information on the therapeutic properties of drugs. Muhammad Yusif Shirvani used grape vinegar, small walnut juice, mustard, white lime, berries, garlic, mulberry leaves, black pepper, blackberry root, peas, ginger, sumac, pomegranate root, tarragon and other rose water. used ingredients. As a form of medicine, he used ores, decoctions, ointments, patches, pills, pastes.

The book gives a brief information about the diseases of all parts of the human body, treatment, drugs and their composition, preparation and effects.

As in the pages of Eastern medical literature, the book "Tibbname" says that when treating or giving medicine to patients, "with God's help he will be healed," "God heal."

The book notes that diseases and their treatment methods are often self-correcting. So, it would be good if today's doctors learn the treatments and methods of the past and use them at the level of modern understanding.

In the introduction to the book, Muhammad Yusuf called his work the Book of Wisdom. At the same time, he writes, "I worked as a doctor for Lutfali Bey, the master of Shirvan. After the ruler of Shirvan, Huseyn khan Lutfali bey, was arrested and sent to the Hormoz fortress in Dagestan, I fled in fear. I was in Baghdad and Azerbaijan for a while, then I went to Dagestan. While there, in the Terek fortress, I received the book Tibbname. I copied the whole book that will work one day." The real author of the book is not known, but he is considered to be the author of "Tibbname" because he became famous at the Republican Institute of Manuscripts under the name of Muhammad Yusif. The book provides information on headaches, malculia, epilepsy, insanity, dementia, unconsciousness, forgetfulness, nosebleeds, toothaches, colds, babasil, tuberculosis and other diseases, their treatment and medication.

The translation of a small part of the book "Law" by the invincible and humble teacher Ibn Sina into Azerbaijani by Efendi-zade Mukhtar Ismail oglu / Aghdashli /, the book "Gulshan-ul-Ilaj" in Persian written by Muhammad Tahir ibn Muzaddin in Agdash / h 1255 / m 1839- cu il / da wrote.

Mirza Kazim Tabrizi's book on medicine written in Agdash in 1254 / m 1839, etc. can be shown.

Originally written in 1775/6 by Abulhasan Maraghi, originally from the city of Maragha in South Azerbaijan, "Treatment-munfarida" ("The most perfect treatments") deals with the treatment of various diseases. The book provides detailed information on herbal, animal and mineral medicines and their therapeutic effects. At present, this work has been translated and republished at the Institute of Manuscripts named after Mohammad Fuzuli of ANAS.

In the 18th and 19th centuries, collections of hadiths on the sayings of the Prophet Muhammad and his Companions about medicine were compiled and copied in Azerbaijan. The name of these works was "Tibbi-Nabawi" ("Medical of the Prophet"). The Institute of Manuscripts keeps three different manuscripts of the Tibbi-Nabawi; One of them was transferred by an Azerbaijani secretary named Mohammad Bargushadi.

One of the medical works compiled in the Azerbaijani language in the XIX century is the anonymous book "Nuskhajat". Here are a number of recipes of folk medicine, as well as magic and prayers against various diseases. One of the famous doctors living at that time was Khurshudbanu Natava's palace doctor Mahammadgulu Gayibzade Garabaghi.

Beginning in the 19th century, the influence of European medicine began to be felt in Azerbaijan, and medical science entered a new stage.

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